

Spectrophotometric determination of platinum(IV) using anthranilic acid

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A rapid and sensitive spectrophotometric method for the determination of Pt^{IV} with anthranilic acid is described. Anthranilic acid reacts with Pt^{IV} at pH 3.0 to give a pink coloured complex, which shows λ_{\max} at 372 nm. Sandell's sensitivity and molar absorptivity of the complex are $5.6 \times 10^{-3} \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and $3.41 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The effect of foreign ion and other experimental variables are studied. Pt^{IV} has been successfully determined in synthetic solutions.

Liu *et al.*¹ have reviewed a new system for simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of platinum(IV) and palladium(II). A survey of literature reveals that a large number of reagents, such as *N-m*-methylphenyl-*N'*-(sodium-*p*-aminobenzenesulfonate)thiourea², 2-(2-(5-bromopyridyl)-azo)-5-dimethylaminoaniline³, iodide and rhodamine 6G⁴, 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzaldehydethiosemicarbazone⁵, potassium iodide and diantipyrylmethane⁶, thiocarbonylhydrazide⁷, 2-hydroxy-1-acetonaphthone-thiosemicarbazone⁸, 4,4'-bis(dimethylamino)thiobenzophenone⁹ in presence of ascorbic acid and Tiron X-100, and 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide¹⁰. In the present investigation, anthranilic acid has been used as a sensitive spectrophotometric reagent for the determination of platinum(IV).

Results and Discussion

Anthranilic acid forms a soluble pink coloured 1 : 2 complex with Pt^{IV} having an absorption maximum at 372 nm ($\epsilon = 4.07 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Pt^{IV} reacts with anthranilic acid at 60° for 5 min at pH 3.0. The blank has λ_{\max} at 330 nm.

Beer's law is obeyed up to 48 ppm of Pt^{IV}. The optimum range for accurate determination deduced from Ringbom's plot¹¹ is found to be 8–48 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity¹² for 24 ppm are $3.41 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $5.6 \times 10^{-3} \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The standard deviation calculated for five determinations of 16, 24 and 48 ppm are 0.02, 0.03 and 0.03, respectively. The stability constant¹³ of the platinum-anthranilic acid complex is calculated be 2.6×10^3 .

The effect of varying amount of anthranilic acid on the colour development was studied with a solution containing 24 ppm of Pt^{IV}. Maximum of 6 ml of 0.1% solution of anthranilic acid was needed for the maximum colour development.

The effect of some ions that often associate with Pt^{IV} were studied by adding different amounts to 24 ppm of Pt^{IV} solution. An error of $\pm 3\%$ in the absorbance reading is considered tolerable. The tolerance limits (ppm) of various ions were found to be as follows : Rh^{III}, Ru^{III} (8); Ni^{II}, Co^{II} (10); Os^{VIII} (15); U^{VI} (20); Tl^{III} (50); Cu^{II}, Hg^{II}, Al^{III}, Sn^{IV}, Mo^{VI}, citrate, nitrate, sulfate (100); Cd^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Zr^{IV}, chloride, fluoride, bromide (200); tartrate (300).

Artificial mixtures corresponding to the Pt-Ir, Pt-Rh and Pt-Ni alloy composition were prepared and the platinum content was determined by the proposed method and the relative error was found to be 0.09, 0.20 and 0.07%, respectively (average of 5 determinations).

Conclusions : The reagent provides a simple, rapid and accurate method for the spectrophotometric determination of Pt^{IV}. The reagent has the advantage of high sensitivity,

Table 1. Comparison with other spectrophotometric methods

Reagent	pH	λ_{\max} nm	Beer's law range ppm	Remarks
Iodide and rhodamine 6G ^a	3	575	0.0–0.48	Pd interferences
2-Hydroxy-1-acetonaphthone-thiosemicarbazide ^b	5–6	346	2.34–13.45	Requires pre-heating for colour development
4,4'-Bis-(dimethylamino)-thiobenzophenone ^c	2.8	530	0.0–0.48	Many bivalent ions interfere
4-Phenyl-thiosemicarbazide ^d	3–7	660	up to 6.0	Uses a surfactant
Anthranilic acid ^e	3.0	372	8.0–48.0	Simple, sensitive

^aRef. 4. ^bRef. 8. ^cRef. 9. ^dRef. 10. ^ePresent method.

selectivity and easy availability. The accuracy of the method is comparable with most methods reported in the literature (Table 1). Most of the common metal ions, which are associated with platinum either in mineral or in alloys, do not interfere in its determination and hence the method can be used for the analysis of alloys, minerals and artificial mixtures for their platinum content.

Experimental

All the reagents were of A.R. grade. Standard stock solution (1000 ppm) of platinum(IV) was prepared by dissolution of chloroplatinic acid (Johnson Mathey) in distilled water and standardized gravimetrically¹⁴. It was then suitably diluted to prepare the standard solutions. A 0.1% solution of anthranilic acid was prepared in absolute ethanol. Buffer solutions of suitable pH were prepared by mixing borax, potassium hydrogen phthalate, potassium dihydrogen phosphate, KCl, HCl and NaOH in proper proportion¹⁵.

A Secomam Anthelie NUA022 spectrophotometer was used with 1 cm quartz cell.

Procedure : To aliquots (1.0–6.0 ml) of the stock solution containing 8–48 ppm of Pt^{IV} was added 0.1% anthranilic acid solution (12 ml) and made up to 25 ml using buffer solution of pH 3.0. The solutions were then shaken and the absorbance was measured at 372 nm against the reagent blank.

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